

CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPECIAL TOURISM PRODUCTS OF MU CANG CHAI TOURISM DESTINATION, YEN BAI, VIETNAM

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Summary

The article studies the conditions for developing specific tourism products at the tourist destination of Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai. The quantitative research method was used on a sample of 223 domestic tourists who had visited and experienced Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai, Vietnam. The results show that the 7- condition model has a positive impact and is statistically significant, with the most important being specific tourism resources, policies to develop specific tourism products, tourism infrastructure, tourism human resources, tourism technical facilities, linkage and development cooperation, and tourism demand. On the basis of the obtained results, the study has proposed solutions and recommendations to improve the effectiveness of conditions for developing specific tourism products in the Mu Cang Chai tourist destination, contributing to the promotion of the development of tourism in Yen Bai province in the coming time.

Keywords: Special Tourism Products, Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai, Viet Nam.

1. RATIONALE

The tourism and travel industries are increasingly developing, making an essential contribution to the growth process and economic restructuring in Vietnam. This increasingly enhances the competitiveness of Vietnam in tourism and travel through the continuous improvement of the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index (TTCI) since the first publication of the index in 2007 by the World Economic Forum (WEF) in the Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Report (TTCR).

TTCI measures four important pillars of a country by 14 sub-indices with 90 indicators. Statistics from reports show that Vietnam has advantages in terms of competitive prices, natural resources, and culture but is quite limited in terms of tourism development and sustainability, with priority given to tourism, infrastructure in general, and tourism service infrastructure in particular (WEF 2007–2019).

Specific tourism products have the ability to be personalized, to create attractions and competition, and to become a brand for the destination. With such an important role, the study of specific tourism product development conditions is always a topic that attracts the attention

of many tourism research scholars, policymakers, tourism organizations, institutions, and businesses. This has also become a widely studied topic by many domestic and foreign researchers. The literature review shows that there are still differences in determining the research framework and the system of conditions for developing specific tourism products.

As a matter of fact, there is no method or model that is completely suitable to determine the specific conditions of tourism product development in all tourist destinations at all times. In Vietnam, the development of tourism products in a specific direction with a difference has been posed as an important strategic content of Vietnam's tourism in order to improve competitiveness in the process of global integration both regionally and internationally. In particular, the basic special issue is to build specific products with Vietnamese identity. Tourism products need to reflect the typical nuances of each locality.

As a key tourist destination in the province and influential in the Northwest region, Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai, is a destination with great potential and outstanding strengths to develop specific tourism products. However, the development of specific tourism products in Mu Cang Chai district still has many shortcomings, is not commensurate with the potential and strengths of the district, and has no clear direction.

The basic reason is that Mu Cang Chai tourism has not been oriented to develop in an overall and methodical manner on the basis of available resources, opportunities, and advantages, so it has not been able to concentrate resources with focus. Therefore, the problem is to find the most representative values that are representative, specific, meaningful, and widespread to focus on investing in creation, development, promotion, etc. to become a unique tourism product of Mu Cang Chai.

From here, creating favorable conditions for Mu Cang Chai tourism to develop will contribute to bringing Yen Bai province to the same level as the whole country, promoting the development of Vietnam's economy.

Therefore, to be able to develop more strongly specific tourism products in Mu Cang Chai, it is necessary to determine the conditions for developing specific tourism products here, which has both theoretical and practical significance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Studies Related To Specific Tourism Product Development Conditions

Conditions for developing tourist destinations have been mentioned in many domestic and foreign studies, specifically summarized by the author in the following table:

Table 1: Conditions for Tourism Destination Development

Author	Conditions
Go, and, Govers, (2000).	Destination accessibility; Destination readiness; Service quality; Government support; Price policy; Pictures of the destination; Climatic and environmental conditions; Attractiveness
Sharpley and Telfer (2002)	Create job opportunities; Diversify the economy; Support the development of public services, tourism services, etc.
Wober, K. W. (2002)	Natural and cultural resources; Tourism infrastructure; Human Resources; Tourism market; Geographical environment; etc.
Dwyer and Kim (2003)	Natural resources; Cultural tourism resources; Special event; Supports; Destination management; Demands; Market manifestations
Vu Duc Minh (2008)	Travel resources; Infrastructure for tourism; Tourism demand and demand development; Political security, safety and social order

(Source: Compiled by the author's team)

As can be seen in Table 1, Go and Govers (2000) stated that the conditions for tourism destination development include: Destination accessibility; Destination readiness; Service quality; Government support; Price policy; Pictures of the destination; Climatic and environmental conditions; Attractiveness; etc. Sharpley and Telfer (2002) put forward the view that conditions include: Creating job opportunities; Economic diversification; Supporting the development of public services, tourism services, etc. On the other hand, some other authors, such as Wober, K. W. (2002), Dwyer and Kim (2003), and Vu Duc Minh (2008), focus on the facts about tourism resources, infrastructure for tourism, tourism demand, destination management, etc. It can be seen that the authors are in high agreement, asserting that tourism development and destination development need to be based on different necessary conditions, including conditions on tourism resources; Tourism infrastructure; tourism technical infrastructure; demand and demand for tourism development; policies to support tourism development by the government; etc. This is considered an important premise for developing specific tourism products in a sustainable way.

2.2. Research Related To Mu Cang Chai Tourism Development

For tourism research and development activities in Mu Cang Chai district, up to now, there have been an amount of research works such as Dao Hong Bich (2018), *Solutions to develop agricultural tourism in Mu Cang Chai district - Yen Bai*; Luong Vu Bich Hang (2018), *Developing community tourism business in Mu Cang Chai*; Minh Thuy (2020), *Mu Cang Chai builds a brand for tourism products*; Do Huyen Trang (2021), *Research on community participation in tourism development in Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai*; etc. Those studies initially went into tourism development activities in Mu Cang Chai district but only stopped at qualitative analysis, not in-depth research on the problems posed to tourism development in the district. As for the research and development of special tourism product development conditions in Mu Cang Chai district, there is currently a blank space for this issue. This is an urgent basis for the implementation of the author's research topic.

3. THEORETICAL BASIS

3.1. Special Tourism Products

The specific tourism product is a relatively new concept in Vietnam and is sometimes used in a number of tourism documents without a complete theoretical system. This section aims to summarize some views related to the concept of specific tourism products used in the country and around the world.

In international studies related to this issue, the concept of “special interest tourism” (SIT) seems to be of the most commonly used. According to Derrett (2001), this type of tourism aims to provide entertainment and relaxation experiences that are customized to the unique interests of individuals and groups of tourists. Some travelers who use SIT focus on activities they enjoy in particular (shopping, climbing, skiing, etc.), while others feel the urge to experience a certain destination because of specific elements there (Weiler & Hall, 1992; Swarbrook & Horner, 1999; Rittichainuwat, 2018). In short, “special interest tourism” can be understood as a type of tourism with specific characteristics to serve the special interests of tourists at specific destinations (Jin & Sparks, 2017). Quoted by Wen & Wu, 2020).

In Vietnam, there are also some studies that introduce the concept of specific tourism products. Some emphasize the differences, uniqueness, and outstandingness of tourism resources and services (Pham Trung Luong, 2007; Do Cam Tho, 2009; Cao Hoang Ha, 2021). On the other hand, according to the Vietnam National Administration of Tourism (2016), the attractiveness of specific tourism products depends on the tastes and needs of each tourist market; they may be attractive to one market, but not to another.

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3.2. Developing Specific Tourism Products

“Tourism product development” is a term that has not been widely mentioned. In this regard, the World Tourism Organization (2011) has introduced the concept: “Tourism *product development is a process in which the values of a particular place are used to satisfy the needs of domestic and international tourists. Tourism products may include natural or man-made attractions, hotels, resorts, restaurants, theaters, activities, festivals, and events.*” In Vietnam, the development of specific tourism products has now also been interesting to the Party, the State and researchers. The Vietnam Tourism Development Strategy for the period 2001–20100 and the Vision to 2020 of the Vietnam National Administration of Tourism (2012) have identified: “*Developing sustainable tourism, oriented towards eco-tourism and cultural-historical tourism, ensuring continuous growth, actively contributing to preserving and protecting the natural and social environment, national cultural identity, and building specific,*

high-quality, competitive tourism products in the region and the world.”

In short, the development of specific tourism products must come from the development of tourism products. It means emphasizing the value of the attractiveness, uniqueness, and characteristics of the tourism resources of the destination. Thus, the concept can be formulated as: “Development of specific tourism products is to perfect existing specific tourism products and develop new specific tourism products for that tourist destination”.

4. RESEARCH MODELS AND HYPOTHESES

After acquiring and developing important premises about the conditions for the development of specific tourism products in the direction of sustainability from domestic and foreign studies, the author develops a model with the dependent variable being the development of special tourism products in tourist destination Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai, and seven independent variables that are specific tourism resources, tourism infrastructure, tourism technical facilities, tourism human resources, political policies on developing specific tourism products, tourism demand, and linking and cooperating in developing specific tourism products.

Conditions for specific tourism resources: Tourism resources are considered a prerequisite for the development of specific tourism products. In order to develop specific tourism products, data resources are also required to be different and special. Depending on the uniqueness and characteristics of tourism resources, it is possible to exploit and develop specific tourism products of international, national, regional, or local significance.

We have hypothesis H1:

H1: Specific tourism resources have a direct and positive impact on the development of specific tourism products at Mu Cang Chai and Yen Bai tourist destinations.

Conditions on tourism infrastructure: Infrastructure includes transportation systems, electricity systems, water supply and drainage systems, and communication systems. Infrastructure plays an important role in creating specific tourism products as well as satisfying the needs of tourists because the infrastructure elements help ensure the essential and basic elements that help visitors access and experience specific tourism products. Depending on whether the particular tourism product has international, national, regional, or local significance, it is necessary to establish an appropriate infrastructure system. For example, if a particular product has international and national significance, it is necessary to develop an air and sea transport network to easily access and welcome international and domestic tourism destinations throughout the country. If it is a specific product of regional or local significance, it is only necessary to strongly develop the road network to easily allow visitors to move and access local or regional destinations.

We have hypothesis H2:

H2: Tourism infrastructure has a direct and positive impact on the development of specific tourism products in the tourist destination of Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai.

Conditions on tourism infrastructure: tourism infrastructure includes a system of tourist accommodation establishments, dining establishments, entertainment establishments, etc. Each department has a certain role and position in the system. The tourism system has the ability to make different decisions on the exploitation and development of specific tourism products. In order to develop specific tourism products internationally and across the country, it requires tourism technical infrastructure to develop commensurately and synchronously with local cultural characteristics to exploit specific tourism resources and attract tourists, especially as an international tourist resort or a fastidious domestic tourist destination with the ability to pay only high prices. The evaluation of tourism's technical infrastructure is based on three criteria: (1) ensuring good conditions for tourism relaxation; (2) achieving optimal economic efficiency in the process of building and exploiting technical infrastructure; and (3) making it convenient for guests' travel from places to destinations. We have hypothesis H3:

H3: Tourism infrastructure has a direct and positive impact on the development of specific tourism products at the tourist destination of Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai.

Conditions on tourism human resources: Humans play an important role in the exploitation and development of tourism products in general and are extremely important in the development of specific tourism products. Human resources not only play the role of selecting and connecting factors to create specific products and sustainable development but also play an important role in maintaining, preserving, and creating cultural spaces with unique characteristics. Bold identity to create a truly unique and impressive set of specific tourism products for visitors. Therefore, human resources for developing specific data products are not only guaranteed in quantity but also have to be really high-qualified human resources, fully converging the conditions of awareness, expertise, skills, attitudes, and discipline at work. We have hypothesis H4:

H4: Tourism human resources have a direct and positive impact on the development of specific tourism products at Mu Cang Chai and Yen Bai tourist destinations.

Conditions on specific tourism product development policies: To develop specific tourism products, it is necessary to develop tourism development policies in general and specific tourism products in particular in accordance with the reality of each locality. In fact, there are many tourism development policies, of which some key ones must be mentioned, such as immigration policy, marketing policy, training policy, tax policy, infrastructure development investment policy, policies to attract investment and develop tourism economic infrastructure, etc. Thus, the development of specific tourism products in a sustainable direction can focus on five basic policies, which are policies to encourage and support the development of tourism products. Particularly, policies on the attraction of investment to develop specific tourism products, policies on training human resources in tourism, policies on the promotion of specific tourism products, and policies on association and cooperation in the development of specific tourism products.

We have hypothesis H5:

H5: The policy of developing specific tourism products has a direct and positive impact on the development of specific tourism products in the tourist destination of Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai.

Conditions on tourist demand: In order to form and develop a particular specific tourism product, it is necessary to have the solvency demand of tourists. Specific tourism products will not be able to supply the market if it is not impressive, attractive, and attracts customers. Thus, the more favorable the conditions for tourism demand, especially the demand for specific tourism products, the more favorable the development of those products will be. We have hypothesis H6:

H6: Tourism demand has a direct and positive impact on the development of specific tourism products in Mu Cang Chai and Yen Bai tourist destinations.

Conditions for association and cooperation in developing specific tourism products: Developing specific tourism products in a sustainable way requires the close association and cooperation of localities. The cooperation and association are expressed in many aspects: building specific tourism products with an inter-regional nature; human resource training; promoting and promoting tourism; etc., in order to create a brand and competitive advantage for the whole region. We have hypothesis H7:

H7: Linking and cooperating to develop specific tourism products has a direct and positive impact on the development of specific tourism products at Mu Cang Chai and Yen Bai tourist destinations.

From here, the author proposes the research model shown in Figure 1 below:

(Source: Authors' proposal)

Figure 1: Research Model of Specific Tourism Product Development Conditions of Mu Cang Chai and Yen Bai Tourist Destinations

5. RESEARCH METHODS

Inheriting and developing the scale of components to form the proposed questionnaire The author conducted interviews and discussions with seven experts, including two experts working at the Department of Culture and Information of Mu Cang Chai district, Yen Bai; two experts are local guides; one expert works at Thuongmai University (TMU); one expert is the owner of Pu Nhu homestay; and one expert is the homestay owner at Mountainview Khau Pha. On this basis, a set of official scales including 33 observed variables was determined, of which 30 were for 7 independent variables and 3 were for dependent variables.

In this study, to ensure the survey sample size, the research team used the calculation method of Bollen (1998). The calculation will be $n \times 5$ observations (where n is the parameter to estimate or the total number of scales for the independent variables). Thus, the sum of the scales is $30 \times 5 = 150$ observations for domestic tourists. However, to ensure objectivity and accuracy, the research team distributed 250 questionnaires. Therefore, the authors' group distributed 250 vouchers to domestic tourists and collected 223 votes (89.2% rate) to ensure the requirements of the total and structure of the observed sample size. Thus, the sample size used for processing is 223 tickets from domestic tourists.

Regarding data analysis, the main quantitative analyses in the study include testing the reliability of the scale through Cronbach's alpha coefficient, exploratory factor analysis (EFA), correlation analysis, and multivariate regression. The analytical support software is SPSS 26. The recommendations on thresholds to ensure relevance and reliability are derived from the studies of Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), Hair et al. (1995), and Gerbing and Anderson (1988).

6. RESEARCH RESULTS

6.1. Checking The Reliability Of The Scale Through Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient

The scales will be tested using Cronbach's alpha tool. Cronbach's alpha will help eliminate unsatisfactory observed variables or unsatisfactory scales in the research process.

The results of the evaluation of the reliability coefficient of Cronbach's with the correlation coefficients of the total matched observed variables are greater than 0.3, and the observed variables in the scales are all greater than 0.6. Specifically, eight factors were tested: natural resources, infrastructure, facilities, human resources, policies, tourism demands, linkage, and satisfaction, with Cronbach's alpha values of 0.892, respectively: 0.836; 0.849; 0.795; 0.859; 0.786; 0.779; 0.868. Thus, all scales are reliable and suitable for inclusion in EFA exploratory factor analysis.

6.2. Efa Exploratory Factor Analysis

EFA was performed with the aim of determining the factors to be retained in the model and the valid observed variables. The results of EFA factor analysis (using varimax rotation) showed that the KMO coefficient of 0.921 was satisfactory, seven factors extracted at Eigenvalue were $1,122 > 1$, and the total variance extracted was $66.358\% > 50\%$. Thus, the observed variables are satisfactory and meaningful.

6.3. Correlation Test

Analyze the correlation between the dependent variable (visitor satisfaction) and the independent variables. Pearson correlation analysis is used in this section to consider the fit when adding components to the regression model. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is used to quantify the closeness of the linear relationship between two quantitative variables. The absolute value of r indicates the degree of closeness of the linear relationship ($r \leq 0.3$: weak correlation; $0.3 < r < 0.5$: relatively close correlation; $r \geq 0.5$: correlation rigid).

The sig value indicates whether the relationship between the observed variables is statistically significant or not. Here, the sig value is 0.01, showing that all the independent variables have a relationship with the dependent variable at a 99% significance level and are all positive relationships. Dependent variable Development of specific tourism products at tourist destinations Mu Cang Chai in Yen Bai has a strong correlation with the variables: natural resources, infrastructure, human resources, policies, tourism demands, and linkages.

6.4. Regression Model

Regression analysis will determine the causal relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables and also consider multicollinearity between the independent variables. Regression analysis was performed by the Enter method, and the variables were included at the same time to select based on the criteria for the exclusion of variables with a sig. > 0.05 . The values $R^2 = 0.780$ and adjusted $R^2 = 0.765$ mean that 76.5% of the variation in the development of specific tourism products in the tourist destination Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai, is explained by the independent variables in the frame study.

Table 2: Multivariate Regression Analysis Results

Scales	The system has not been standardized		Normalization coefficient	T - value	Sig. level	Multicollinear Statistics	
	Regressionon weight	Standard deviation	Beta			Acceptance factor	VIF
Constant	.288	.348		.826	.041		
Natural resources	.557	.097	.479	5.728	.000	.306	1.273
Infrastructure	.206	.097	.167	2.119	.000	.342	1.925
Facilities	.039	.069	.138	1.557	.000	.452	1.215
Human resources	.103	.100	.153	2.030	.000	.428	1.337
Policies	.246	.085	.211	2.887	.000	.399	1.509
Tourism demands	.077	.085	.115	.908	.003	.588	1.374
Linkages	.129	.083	.124	1.556	.001	.421	1.700

(Source: Data processing results from SPSS 26.0 of the research team)

Test of error independence: Durbin-Watson statistical quantity (d) can be used to test the correlation of adjacent errors (first-order series correlation). The quantity d has a value ranging

from 0 to 4. If the residuals have no first-order series correlation, the value of d will be close to 2 (Hoang Trong and Chu Nguyen Mong Ngoc, 2008). The results show that the quantity $d = 1,723$, which is close to the value 2, so it can be concluded that the residuals have no first-order series correlation with each other. The results of testing the assumptions of the regression model drawn from the Enter method also show that the assumptions are not violated and there is no multicollinearity because the VIF is less than 10.

The regression model to assess the impact of specific tourism product development conditions at the destination Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai, is rewritten as follows:

$$\text{DSTP} = 0.479 \cdot \text{TR} + 0.167 \cdot \text{TI} + 0.138 \cdot \text{TT} + 0.153 \cdot \text{HR} + 0.211 \cdot \text{TP} \\ + 0.115 \cdot \text{TD} + 0.124 \cdot \text{LT}$$

6.5. Discussing Research Results

Table 2 shows that the regression coefficients all have positive signs, which is consistent with the theory, reflecting the explanatory variables positively correlated to the development of specific tourism products in the destination Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai.

From the results of multivariate regression analysis, it is shown that all 7 conditions included in the analytical model have a positive impact on the development of destination-specific tourism products in Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai. It means, the conditions of unique *Tourism resources* have coefficient impact of 0.479, which is the most important of the seven conditions included in the analytical model. Next is the condition about specific *tourism product development policy*, which has an impact coefficient of 0.211; conditions about *tourism infrastructure* have an coefficient impact of 0.167; conditions about *tourism human resources* have coefficient impact of 0.153; conditions about *tourism technical facilities* have an impact factor of 0.138; conditions *about cooperating to develop specific tourism product* have an impact factor of 0.124; and conditions about *tourism demand* have an impact factor of 0.115.

7. SOME SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS TO DEVELOP SPECIFIC TOURISM PRODUCTS IN MU CANG CHAI, YEN BAI TOURIST DESTINATION

Firstly, Exploit and Conserve Tourism Resources

In the process of exploiting tourism resources towards the addition and enhancement of unique tourism products with their own identity and high competitiveness, Mu Cang Chai also needs to develop typical unique tourism products of the district, focus on developing tourism products with potential, take advantage of tourism resources to develop mainstream tourism products of Mu Cang Chai, exploit and develop other complementary tourism products, and develop new tourism products:

- Building typical unique tourism products of the district: “Discover special national landscapes of Mu Cang Chai terraces and natural landscapes associated with adventure tourism development; learn about the cultural identity of the ethnic group (H’Mong people, etc.)”.

- Focusing on developing tourism products with potential and strengths to develop into mainstream tourism products in Mu Cang Chai, such as festival tourism, community tourism, and adventure sports tourism, etc.
- Exploiting and developing other complementary tourism products, such as historical-cultural tourism, etc.
- Developing new tourism products such as ecotourism, agriculture, etc.

Mu Cang Chai also needs to be determined to implement roadmaps to successfully develop national tourist sites, new world heritage sites, and specific tourism products according to the plan, such as making *Thổi Kèn* (a kind of bamboo flute playing) and *Đàn Môi* (lip lute) become national intangible cultural heritage by 2025; turning the Che Tao species and habitat conservation area into a world biosphere reserve by 2025; and so on. At the same time, continue to evaluate, plan, develop, and upgrade new tourism resources in the whole district. Expediting dossiers to request UNESCO recognize the scenic Mu Cang Chai terraced fields as a UNESCO World Heritage Site in the Mekong Delta as a world cultural heritage, etc.

In addition, to ensure the prevention of resource degradation and environmental pollution, and to ensure the sustainable development of tourism in Bac Kan in general, it is necessary to consider the following solutions: clear and effective land use planning is needed to avoid overlapping; strictly implement the Law on Environmental Protection; strictly protect the tourist environment in areas such as special national relic Mu Cang Chai terraced fields, scenic spots, historical and cultural relics, etc.; there are regulations on compulsorily making environmental impact assessment reports for all socio-economic development investment projects in general and tourism in particular; improve environmental troubleshooting techniques; strengthen propaganda to protect tourism resources and the environment.

Second, Strengthen Policies to Develop Specific Tourism Products

Mu Cang Chai needs to strengthen policies to develop specific tourism products. Specifically: strengthening policies to encourage and support people to participate in the conservation and promotion of local traditional cultural and heritage values; strengthening policies to support the community and create jobs for local people; strengthening policies to attract tourism investment projects, etc.

Third, Invest and Attract Investment in Tourism Infrastructure

The People's Committee of Mu Cang Chai district needs to carefully consider the investment and attraction of investment in tourism infrastructure development. Due to limited resources, in addition to the capital from the local investment budget, the district needs to make good use of public-private partnership capital, call for private investment, socialize investment, etc. Investment and attracting investments need to be synchronized, concentrated, and gathered. In addition, the attraction of investment also needs to strictly adhere to the viewpoint of only approving investors whose investment projects ensure environmental specifications and do not cause harm to living fauna. In addition, the locality also needs to require investors to commit to creating employment and income opportunities for local people when the project is built,

completed, and put into operation. Only in this way will the investment and development of specific tourism products in the locality contribute to ensuring sustainability in terms of economy, culture, society, and the environment.

Fourth, Improve the Quality of Tourism Human Resources

First of all, the recruitment of management tourism human resources needs to ensure the right expertise, qualifications, skills, etc. to really be capable of planning and developing specific tourism products for Mu Cang Chai. In addition, the district's tourism department also needs to regularly train and foster state management knowledge in tourism, knowledge of building and developing tourism products, etc., for the state management staff. The district also needs to closely coordinate with local tourism associations and business establishments in the spirit of sharing funds to support organizing classes and training for individual workers. Motion. At the same time, increase practical and appropriate training programs for households participating in community tourism.

Fifth, Improve Tourism Technical Facilities

In order to support the development of specific tourism products that are meaningful to serve international tourism and tourism throughout the country, communes in the district need to focus on attracting investment in the system of accommodation and catering establishments. Each commune needs to have a high-quality accommodation system to meet the needs of guests. On the other hand, the investment and attraction of investment in the construction of tourist areas also need to adhere to the point of view of creating specificity and avoiding duplication with communes in the district. At the same time, Mu Cang Chai also needs to promote investment in completing technical infrastructure for tourism development, such as parking lots, scenic spots, service areas, etc., in key tourist areas and destinations of the district: Khau Pha Pass; La Pan Tan hill tourist attraction; Dinosaur Back Mountain, De Xu Phinh Commune; Sang Nhu Horseshoe Field, Mo De Commune; terraced fields, ancient stone fields in Ta Ghenh village, Lao Chai commune... Invest in upgrading and building new service infrastructure to serve tourists such as: health care, banks, tourist information centers, tourist attractions, and tourist attractions. Stops, internet access points, etc. In addition, the district needs to add more sports, entertainment, and shopping services for tourists to prolong their stay and enrich the products. Tourism.

Sixth, Strengthen Links and Cooperation to Develop Specific Tourism Products

Mu Cang Chai needs to actively link and cooperate in developing regional tourism, especially in the Northern Midlands and Mountains, effectively connecting with tourism in the Red River Delta, Hanoi - Hai Phong - Quang Ninh - Ninh Binh; the southern provinces; and the eight Northwest provinces expanded with Ho Chi Minh City. In order to improve the quality and position of tourism in Yen Bai province in general, Mu Cang Chai district in particular needs to participate in building and promoting tourism on the "Northwest Heritage Road", associated with the chain of tourism products in the Northwest region, with its own characteristics but still ensuring its own local identity. In addition, it is also necessary to focus on building international tourism cooperation relationships with sister provinces, countries, regions and territories such

as Val de marne province, Chevilly Larue city (French Republic); province of Vientiane, Xay Nha Bu Ly (Laos); Yunnan province (China); Mimasaki city, Okayama (Japan); Korea, ASEAN, etc.

Seventh, Develop Tourism Demands

The district should organize tourism weeks to stimulate tourism demand and build tourism products at reasonable costs and with many incentives through specific actions: calling for management units and business units to apply discount programs for rooms, transportation fees, free shuttles, etc. for visitors with appropriate requirements; promoting advertising from the community; strengthening tourism promotion and propaganda in the media of the province and the district. In addition, it is necessary to develop a specific plan for product development, marketing, promotion, and branding to have a basis for implementing orientation in each period. The plan to promote, promote, and build a tourism brand should be carried out methodically and professionally on the basis of attaching and promoting the brands of specific and main products of Mu Cang Chai. In particular, with the epidemic situation still complicated, the district needs to research and develop new tourism products such as eco-tourism, experiencing and discovering nature, and tourism products associated with OCOP and COVID-19. With the development of online tourism applications, accommodation units in the district should consider posting information about the promotion program of Mu Cang Chai Tourism Week on tourism websites such as Agoda, Travekola, etc. to reach more tourists.

CONCLUSION

Developing specific tourism products in a sustainable way is the core factor for sustainable tourism development in each locality. Therefore, it is necessary to study the specific conditions of tourism product development, assess the situation, and propose appropriate recommendations to develop specific tourism products for each locality. This study develops a research model and tests hypotheses based on meaningful responses from 223 respondents, who are domestic tourists who have visited and experienced specific tourism products of the destination. To Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai. The results demonstrate that the model fits the sample, and the results can provide a reliable reference for the tourism administrators in the tourist destination Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai, to increase the development of tourism activities and specific tourism products in a sustainable way.

This study identifies seven conditions to ensure the development of specific tourism products in the Mu Cang Chai tourist destination in Yen Bai, including specific tourism resources, specific tourism product development policies, and specific tourism product development policies, tourism infrastructure, tourism human resources, tourism material and technical facilities, linkage and cooperation in developing specific tourism products, and tourism bridges. The results from the study have shown that specific tourism resources have the strongest impact on the development of specific tourism products in the tourist destination of Mu Cang Chai, Yen Bai. This implies that the most important thing to do to develop specific tourism products at the Mu Cang Chai tourist destination is to focus on and promote the exploitation and conservation of tourism resources in the district to promote the strengths of

specific tourism products that are available and at the same time create new and unique specific tourism products for the locality, contributing to ensuring the sustainability of both the economy, culture, society, and the environment.

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